

Data Fabric Service Platform

v1

Including configured RWL Interoperability Use Cases

30 September 2025

The Data Fabric Service Platform can be accessed by the public and by the project stakeholders via this website: <https://directed.dev.52north.org/>

For each of the four DIRECTED Real Word Labs tailored interoperability use cases are configured that directly answer to requests and user stories documented in D5.2 the Low Level Design of the Data Fabric. For technical descriptions of the Data Fabric, please be also referred to D5.1. Matters of data protection and ethics are discussed in D5.3. The development and implementation approach is documented in D5.4. A user manual and further training material is forthcoming, now that the Data Fabric has been released in Version 1.

The development of the Data Fabric has been collaboratively made within the GitHub organization DIRECTED at <https://github.com/directedproject-eu>. The source code is organized in different git repositories, i.e the back-end is distributed across several repositories within the DIRECTED organization to support the service oriented architecture and modularity of the RWL specific use cases.

Partners

